
**RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY OF DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY
AND INFORMATION SCIENCE OF SAVITRIBAI PHULE PUNE
UNIVERSITY, PUNE (SPPU)**

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7205262

Abstract:

An institution's academic progress is reflected in its research productivity. The current study attempted to investigate the research contribution of Savitribai Phule Pune University's library and information science department. The Ph.D. thesis records were extracted using the Shodhganga e-theses and dissertation databases. A total of 82 theses were obtained from the SPPU's LIS departments under Shodhganga repository. The study examined all LIS department records available in the Shodhganga repository from 1977 to 2021. MS-Excel was used to extract the data, after which it was analysed using various formulas. The study's major findings revealed that 2008 was the most productive year for the LIS department in terms of research. Dr. Neela J. Deshpande guided 15.85% of Ph.D. theses in the LIS department. Male researchers and guides predominate in the LIS department; 67% of males are research guides and 66% are research scholars. The majority of Ph.D. candidates organised their work into six chapters.

Keywords: Department of LIS; Ph.D.; Research productivity; Shodhganga; SPPU.

Introduction:

LIS research in India began in the early 1930s with the initiative of Dr. S.R. Ranganathan, who promoted the library movement (Maity & Hatua, 2015). The direction of LIS research has shifted over time. The evolution of computers and the internet altered the face of libraries and LIS research. "The discipline of Library and Information Science (LIS) has grown more divided into the sub disciplines of Library Science and Information Science" (Lund, 2020). There are several tools available to assess research productivity and trends. An individual, institution, or nation's academic progress is measured by

their research productivity (Tomei et al., 2014). The tools used to evaluate the results of research include scientometry, bibliometry, and content analysis. Many Indian universities now conduct high-quality research in the area of library and information science. The evaluation of the institute's research productivity indicates the quantity, quality, growth, and current position of research. It also helps to identify research gaps in each area that need to be addressed in the future.

The research productivity of the institution/university reflects the quality of that institute. There are numerous tools available to assess an institution's

productivity in terms of research. An institution's research output includes research articles, projects, doctoral theses, and dissertations. SPPU is one of Maharashtra's oldest state universities. There are a number of universities in Maharashtra that provide LIS education, but SPPU's department of library and information science is the oldest. In 1958, SPPU launched a diploma programme in LIS, and in 1965, they started a bachelor's programme. The LIS department contributes significantly to research. This department has produced 85 LIS professionals who have earned their Ph.D.s.

Shodhganga:

Shodhganga is a digital repository of Indian Electronic Theses and Dissertations set up by the INFLIBNET Centre. Shodhganga has provided open access to electronic theses of all the universities and centres registered under the UGC. As per the amendment made in the Minimum Standards & Procedure for Award of M.Phil./Ph.D Degree Regulation, 2009 on May 5, 2016, it is mandatory for researchers to submit the electronic copy of theses to the shodhganga through their university. Shodhganga is one of India's largest repositories of electronic theses and dissertations. It also has the ability to capture, index, store, disseminate, and preserve ETDs (Electronic Theses and Dissertations) submitted by the researchers. Shodhganga shows the academic and research progress of each university and department. It also provides a simple and advanced search facility, and researchers can browse the data through universities and departments.

Savitribai Phule Pune University has contributed 11894 theses and

dissertations till date. The department of library and information science contributed 85 theses to Shodhganga. The research contribution of the Department of LIS is appreciable as compared to other universities in Maharashtra.

Objectives:

1. To access the most leading research guides in the Department of LIS of SPPU
2. To know the broad area of research of Department of LIS
3. To find out gender wise research contribution in Department of LIS
4. To know the chapter scheme pattern used by researchers in the Department of LIS
5. To know the most productive year in terms of research for the Department of LIS

Methodology:

The current study attempted to analyse a Ph.D. thesis submitted to Shodhganga repository by Savitribai Phule Pune University's department of library and information science. All thesis data was collected from the shodhganga website

(<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>). It shows total 85 records of theses, but there are 3 duplicate entries. So in this study we are considering the department of library and information science submitted 82 theses to the shodhganga electronic thesis and dissertation database. All of the data was extracted into Excel and analyzed using various formulas.

Scope and Limitations:

The current study only included 82 doctoral theses available in Shodhganga e-theses database under the Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, department of library and information science. The study

examined all of the theses accessible in Shodhganga under the SPPU's department of library and information science until 2022.

Review of Literature:

(Sheikh & Jan, 2017) explored the "research productivity of LIS schools in Pakistan". According to the study, 87 percent of total Ph.D. thesis were completed in the last five years, indicating that LIS schools' research productivity has increased. (Maity & Hatua, 2015) examined doctoral theses from the databases INDCAT, Vidyandhi, and INFLIBNET. From 1950 to 2012, a total of 1058 records were extracted. According to the study, research trends in library management have increased since the IT revolution.(Manjunatha,2019) investigated the LIS department's research contribution at Karnataka State Universities. The study concentrated on university-level research outcomes, leading research guides in the LIS community, and the number of theses published by LIS departments each year. The Shodhganga ETD database contained

a total of 209 theses, which were analysed and extracted.

(Atapour, Hamdipour, & Shenavar, 2022) assessed the research productivity of the Middle Eastern LIS department. The data was obtained from the Web of Science database, and the analysis was carried out with the help of the journal citation report. According to the study, Ilan University has the highest research productivity.(Satija, 1999) described the beginnings of LIS education and Ph.D. programmes in India, as well as Dr. S.R. Ranganathan's contribution to shaping the LIS profession. The author listed the research contributions of Indian universities in the form of Ph.D. theses. The study also identified the major areas of research in library and information science. The current study examined several research articles. They discovered that while many studies have been conducted on research productivity, the department of LIS at SPPU's remains unstudied. As a result, researchers conducted this study.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: The most leading research guides in the Department of LIS of SPPU

Sr. No.	Research Guide	Num. of Students	Percentage
1	Deshpande, N J	13	15.85
2	Patil, Suresh K	12	14.63
3	Singh Surya Nath	11	13.41
4	Konnur, M B	8	9.75
5	Prasad, A R D	8	9.75
6	Mahajan, S G	6	7.31
7	Ganpule, S R	5	6.09
8	Riswadkar, M R	5	6.09
9	Bansode, Sadanand Y.	3	3.65
10	Panage B M	3	3.65

Table No. 1 reflects the top ten research guides at SPPU's Department of LIS. According to the data retrieved from the Shodhganga theses and dissertation

repository, there are a total of 16 research guides. Dr. Neela J. Deshpande secured first place, with 13 (15.85%) students having completed their Ph.D. under her

supervision. While Prof. Dr. S.K. Patil has 12 (14.63%), and Prof. Dr. Singh Surya Nath has 11 (13.41%), research students

have received Ph.D. degrees under their supervision.

Table No. 2. Broad area of research in department of LIS of SPPU

Sr. No.	Area of Research	No. of theses
1	Library and Information Services	10
2	ICT	8
3	Knowledge Management System	6
4	Use Study	5
5	User Study	4
6	Information system	3
7	Human resource planning	3
8	Library Networking	3
9	Ontology, Taxonomy	3
10	Public libraries	3

Table No.2 shows the broad area of research which was studied in the LIS department of SPPU. The Highest 10 researchers were carried out their research

on library and information services, followed by ICT use in library (8) and Knowledge Management system (6).

Table No.3. Gender wise research contribution in Department of LIS of SPPU

Gender	Research Guides	Researchers	Total
Male	12 (75%)	54 (66%)	66 (67%)
Female	4 (25%)	28 (34%)	32 (33%)
Total	16	82	98

Table No. 3 shows the gender-wise distribution of research contributions at SPPU's Department of LIS. It reveals that male research guides predominate in the Department of LIS (12, 75%). 54 students were guided by male research guides. Only

4 (25%) female research guides guided the 28 students. In terms of research, there are 54 male researchers (66%) and 28 female researchers (34%). There is a 67% male contribution to research and a 33% female contribution.

Table No. 4. Chapter scheme pattern used by researchers in the Department of LIS

Sr. No.	No. of Chapters	No. of Thesis
1	4	1
2	5	11
3	6	38
4	7	25
5	8	2
6	9	1
7	11	2
8	12	1
9	13	1

Table No.3 depicts the chapter scheme pattern used by LIS researchers. There are a minimum of 4 chapters and a maximum of 13 chapters in the thesis. For

thesis writing, the majority of researchers (38) used 6-chapter schemes, while 25 used 7-chapter schemes.

Table No.5 The most productive year in terms of research for the Department of LIS of SPPU

Sr. No.	No of Thesis	Ph.D. Completed Year
1	9	2008
2	7	2011
3	6	2014
4	5	2010
5	5	2009
6	5	2005
7	4	2007
8	4	1998
9	3	2017
10	3	2016

Table No. 5 illustrates the Department of LIS's most productive year in terms of research contribution. The Department of LIS completed 82 Ph.D.s

over a 45-year period, from 1977 to 2021. In 2008, nine researchers received their Ph.D. 7, 6 and 5 researchers received their Ph.D. degrees in 2011, 2014, and 2010.

Findings:

- It is found that total of 82 research students have completed Ph.D. in Department of LIS of SPPU from the last 45 years.
- It has been noted that the main areas of research in the LIS department at SPPU include ICT and library and information services. 10 Ph.D. candidates conducted research on libraries and information services, and 8 on ICT.
- The analysis shows that Dr. Neela J. Deshpande is the leading research guide in the Department of LIS of SPPU who has guided 13 (15.85%) research students.
- In terms of research contribution, males are dominated in both roles, as research guides and as researchers. In the SPPU department of LIS, the

majority of research guides (75%) are male and only 25% are female. On the other hand, 66% of researchers are male, while 34% are female.

- The current study reveals that, more than 46% of researchers have written their Ph.D. theses with six chapters, and 30% have made seven chapters to present their Ph.D. research work. As a result, it has been discovered that a six-chapter scheme is most familiar to the majority of research scholars.
- In terms of Ph.D. research, the 2008 year was the most productive year for the department of LIS at SPPU. Nine research scholars received their Ph.D. degrees in 2008. It is also worth noting that the LIS

department's research contribution has increased since 2005.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

Shodhganga is now a key database for every researcher to browse and explore previous research work related to his or her study. INFLIBNET plays a significant role in improving research quality and services in India. SPPU is one of Maharashtra's oldest universities, and it is well known for providing high-quality higher education and research. According to a study, the Department of LIS's research contribution has been increasing since 2005. The quality of the institution and the department determine an institution's research productivity. Each university in India is responsible for showcasing their research outcomes through Shodhganga.

The UGC has taken the lead and published a draft for all universities and research institutions to submit e-copies of theses to the Shodhganga e-theses and dissertation repository. As a result, each university should update and maintain the data as it is published. The LIS department should increase the intake of research guides and encourage LIS students to pursue their Ph.D.; this will automatically increase the department's research productivity. In addition, the LIS department organises research awareness programmes for students to motivate them to explore new areas of LIS.

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